

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Elnoubi****FIRST NAME: Metwalli****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Pr Cleenewerck****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2013 on Windows 7)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- The three kinds of questions that researchers ask are:**
 - Conceptual Questions: What Should We Think?
 - Practical Questions: What Should We Do?
 - Applied Questions: What Must We Understand Before We Know What to Do?
 - All of the above.**¹
- In developing and presenting the literature review of your dissertation chapter (2), you have to:**
 - Provide an understanding of the function and purpose of a literature review (the "what?").

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16–17.

- Describe the role of a research-based critical literature review in a dissertation (the "why?").
 - Provide the skills related to the various steps involved in conducting and presenting a thorough and systematic review of the literature, including identifying and retrieving relevant material and sources; analyzing, evaluating, and synthesizing ideas found in the literature; and developing a conceptual framework (the "how?").
 - All of the above.**²
3. **The first chapter of your dissertation is the introduction to your study, and some of this chapter objectives to:**
- Narrow and refine the problem statement, Develop a purpose statement that addresses the problem, and identify the research questions that are tied to the purpose and, when answered, shed light on the problem.**³
 - Introduce yourself.
 - Introduce your research idea.
 - All of the above.
4. **Information that required in Citations, must answer these questions:**
- Who wrote, edited, or translated the text (sometimes all three)? And what data identify the text?
 - Who published the text and when? And where can the text be found?
 - All of the above.**⁴

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*, 1 edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008), 46.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 33.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition*, 87.

- None of the above.
5. **Information that describes who the participants in your study are, where they come from, some of their history and/or background, education, and personal information such as age, gender, and ethnicity.**
- Contextual Information.
- Perceptual Information.
- Demographic Information.**⁵
- Theoretical Information.
6. **What is the template for notes entries for a book with two authors?**
- Names for first and second authors and page numbers.
- Family names for the two authors and book title.
- Family names, page number, and title of the book.
- ##. Author #1's First and Last Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Sub title of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), XX–XX. Where ## stands for footnote number, and XX stands for page numbers actually cited.**⁶
7. **What suggests the findings are accurate and credible from the standpoint of the researcher, the participants, and the reader?**
- Dependability.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 70.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth Edition, 91.

- Credibility.**⁷
 - Conformability.
 - Transferability
8. **The reasonableness of a recommendation depends on:**
- Being logically and clearly derived from the findings.
 - Being both content- as well as context-specific, and, most important.
 - Being practical; that is, it is capable of implementation.
 - All of the above.**⁸
9. **What is the template for reference list entries citations for a book with a single author?**
- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Sub title of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.**⁹
 - Author's first name and page number.
 - Author's first name, last name, and page number.
 - All of the above.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 86.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 158.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition*, 129.

10. **What is the template for reference list entries citations for a Journal Article Online?**

- Author's first name and URL.
- Author's first name, last name and URL.
- Author's first name, last name and journal volume number.
- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. "Title of Article: Sub title of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number (Additional Date Information): YY–YY. Accessed Date of Access. URL. Where YY stands for a full span of page numbers for an article or a chapter.¹⁰**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. 1 edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Turabian, A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition, 130.